

A SEMI-ANALYTICAL FINITE ELEMENT METHOD FOR THE ANALYSIS OF FUNCTIONALLY GRADED CIRCULAR PLATES

Chih-Ping Wu^{1,*} and Lu-Ting Yu¹

¹ Department of Civil Engineering, National Cheng Kung University, Tainan 70101, TAIWAN

*Corresponding author (cpwu@mail.ncku.edu.tw)

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ABSTRACT

A weak-form formulation of finite annular prism methods (FAPM) based on Reissner's mixed variational theorem (RMVT), is developed for the three-dimensional (3D) static analysis of bi-directional functionally graded (FG) circular plates with various boundary conditions and under mechanical loads. The material properties of the circular plate are assumed to obey a bi-directional power-law distribution of the volume fractions of the constituents through the radial-thickness surface. These FAPM solutions of the loaded FG circular plates with simply-supported edges are in excellent agreement with the solutions obtained using the 3D analytical approach and two-dimensional advanced plate theories available in the literature.

1 INTRODUCTION

It is well known that fiber-reinforced laminated composite (FRLC) structures have a sudden change in their material properties when they cross the interfaces between adjacent layers due to the fact that two dissimilar materials have bonded together. As a result, residual stresses always concentrate around these interfaces when the FRLC structures are subjected to external mechanical and thermal loads and cause the FRLC structures to be prone to delamination in these areas. Thus, in lieu of FRLC materials, a new class of materials, the so-called functionally graded materials (FGM), was introduced to form various beam-, plate-, and shell-like structures in advanced engineering in order to prevent the above-mentioned weakness that typically occurs in FRLC structures. The material properties of these FGM structures are designed to vary continuously and smoothly with the thickness coordinate according to the predefined distributions of the volume fractions of the constituents. Along with the increasing popularity of FGM structures, the related structural analyses have attracted considerable attention. Some review articles on the theoretical methodologies and numerical models of FGM beams, plates, and shells can be found in the literature [1, 2].

Some two-dimensional (2D) advanced and refined plate theories and the three-dimensional (3D) elasticity theory have been used for assorted mechanical analyses of one-directional functionally graded (FG) circular plates with simply-supported or clamped boundary conditions that are subjected to uniformly distributed loads. Among these, the material properties of the FG circular plate considered in most of the articles were assumed to vary through the thickness direction and remain unchanged over the circumferential-radial surface, which are the so-called one-directional FG circular plates. The articles examining the mechanical behavior of bi-directional FG circular plates are rare in the public literature as compared with those for one-directional FG and laminated composite circular plates.

In order to not only capture the 3D behavior of FGM plates and shells, such as the thickness effect, but also to overcome the restrictions of 3D analytical methods, such as the complicated solution process and difficulty associated with use for one- and multi-directional FG circular plates, on the basis of Reissner's mixed variational theorem (RMVT), Wu and Li [3, 4] developed the finite rectangular prism method (FRPM) and finite cylindrical prism method (FCPM) for the 3D analysis of one-directional FG rectangular plates and cylinders with various boundary conditions, respectively. Implementation of the RMVT-based FRPM and FCPM showed that their solutions are accurate and converge rapidly. In the current article, the RMVT is extended to develop the finite annular prism method (FAPM) for the 3D static analysis of bi-directional FG circular plates with both simply-

supported and clamped boundary conditions. A parametric study with regard to some key effects on the 3D static behavior of bi-directional FG circular plates with various boundary conditions is carried out, such as the material-property gradient indices, aspect ratios, and different boundary conditions.

2 RMVT-BASED FINITE ANNULAR PRISM METHODS

2.1 Kinematic and kinetic assumptions

The displacement and transverse stress components of a typical annular prism of the m^{th} -layer are given by

$$[F^{(e)}(r, \theta, z)]^{(m)} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_d} [\psi^{(e)}(r, z)]_i [F^{(e)}(\theta)]_i^{(m)}, \quad (1)$$

where $(F^{(e)})_i^{(m)}$ with $(i = 1, 2, \dots, n_d)$ are the nodal displacement and transverse stress components of a typical annular prism of the m^{th} -layer of the circular plate, i.e., $(F^{(e)})_i^{(m)} = (u^{(e)})_i^{(m)}, (v^{(e)})_i^{(m)}, (w^{(e)})_i^{(m)}, (\tau_{13}^{(e)})_i^{(m)}, (\tau_{23}^{(e)})_i^{(m)}$, and $(\sigma_3^{(e)})_i^{(m)}$; $(\psi^{(e)})_i^{(m)}$ ($i = 1, \dots, n_d$) are the corresponding shape (or interpolation) functions used to interpolate the primary field variables over the prism domain.

Figure 1: The configuration, cylindrical coordinate system and boundary conditions of a circular plate with a 4x2 mesh of the 8-node FAPM.

The linear constitutive equations of the m^{th} -layer, which are valid for the orthotropic materials, are given by

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(m)} = \mathbf{c}^{(m)} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(m)}, \quad (2)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(m)} = \{\sigma_r^{(m)}, \sigma_\theta^{(m)}, \sigma_z^{(m)}, \tau_{\theta z}^{(m)}, \tau_{rz}^{(m)}, \tau_{r\theta}^{(m)}\}^T$ is the stress vector; $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(m)} = \{\varepsilon_r^{(m)}, \varepsilon_\theta^{(m)}, \varepsilon_z^{(m)}, \gamma_{\theta z}^{(m)}, \gamma_{rz}^{(m)}, \gamma_{r\theta}^{(m)}\}^T$ is the strain components; $\mathbf{c}^{(m)} = [c_{ij}^{(m)}]$, and $c_{ij}^{(m)}$ are the elastic coefficients, which are considered to be independent of the circumferential coordinate in the analysis, while they are variable over the radial-thickness surface of the annular prism (i.e., $c_{ij}^{(m)}(r, z)$).

The strain-displacement relations for a typical annular prism of the m^{th} -layer, based on the assumed displacement components in Eq. (1), are given by

$$[\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_r^{(e)}(r, \theta, z)]^{(m)} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_d} (D_r \psi_i^{(e)}) (u_i^{(e)})^{(m)}, \quad (3)$$

$$[\varepsilon_\theta^{(e)}(r, \theta, z)]^{(m)} = (1/r) \sum_{i=1}^{n_d} (\psi_i^{(e)})(v_i^{(e)}, \theta)^{(m)} + (1/r) \sum_{i=1}^{n_d} (\psi_i^{(e)})(u_i^{(e)})^{(m)}, \quad (4)$$

$$[\varepsilon_z^{(e)}(r, \theta, z)]^{(m)} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_d} (D_z \psi_i^{(e)})(w_i^{(e)})^{(m)}, \quad (5)$$

$$[\gamma_{rz}^{(e)}(r, \theta, z)]^{(m)} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_d} (D_z \psi_i^{(e)})(u_i^{(e)})^{(m)} + \sum_{i=1}^{n_d} (D_r \psi_i^{(e)})(w_i^{(e)})^{(m)}, \quad (6)$$

$$[\gamma_{\theta z}^{(e)}(r, \theta, z)]^{(m)} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_d} (D_z \psi_i^{(e)})(v_i^{(e)})^{(m)} + (1/r) \sum_{i=1}^{n_d} (\psi_i^{(e)})(w_i^{(e)}, \theta)^{(m)}, \quad (7)$$

$$[\gamma_{r\theta}^{(e)}(r, \theta, z)]^{(m)} = (1/r) \sum_{i=1}^{n_d} (\psi_i^{(e)})(u_i^{(e)}, \theta)^{(m)} + \sum_{i=1}^{n_d} (D_r \psi_i^{(e)})(v_i^{(e)})^{(m)} - (1/r) \sum_{i=1}^{n_d} (\psi_i^{(e)})(v_i^{(e)})^{(m)}, \quad (8)$$

where the commas denote partial differentiation with respect to the suffix variables, and $D_r \psi_i^{(e)} = \partial \psi_i^{(e)} / \partial r$, $D_z \psi_i^{(e)} = \partial \psi_i^{(e)} / \partial z$.

Figure 2: The configuration of a typical finite annular prism, (a) R4, (b) R8, (c) R12, (d) T3, (e) T6, and (f) T10.

2.2 The Reissner mixed variational theorem

The Reissner mixed variational theorem is used to derive the static equilibrium equations of the FG circular plate under mechanical loads, and the corresponding energy functional (Π_R) of the loaded plate is written in the form of

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi_R = & \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^R [\sigma_r \varepsilon_r + \sigma_\theta \varepsilon_\theta + \sigma_z \varepsilon_z + \tau_{rz} \gamma_{rz} + \tau_{\theta z} \gamma_{\theta z} + \tau_{r\theta} \gamma_{r\theta} - B(\sigma_{ij})] r dr d\theta dz \\ & - \iint_{\Omega^+} [\bar{q}_k^+(r, \theta) u_k^+(r, \theta, h/2)] r dr d\theta - \iint_{\Omega^-} [\bar{q}_k^-(r, \theta) u_k^-(r, \theta, -h/2)] r dr d\theta \\ & - \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \int_{\Gamma_\sigma} (\bar{t}_k u_k) d\Gamma dz - \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \int_{\Gamma_u} [(u_k - \bar{u}_k) t_k] d\Gamma dz, \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where Ω^+ and Ω^- denote the top and bottom surfaces of the circular plate (i.e., $z = h/2$ and $z = -h/2$), respectively, in which the transverse loads \bar{q}_k^+ and \bar{q}_k^- ($k = r, \theta$ and z) are applied, the

upward ones of which are defined as positive; Γ_σ and Γ_u denote the portions of the edge boundary, in which the surface traction and displacement components (i.e., \bar{t}_k and \bar{u}_k ($k= r, \theta$ and z)) are prescribed, respectively. $B(\sigma_{ij})$ is the complementary energy density function.

In the current formulation, the RMVT is used, such that the displacement and transverse stress components are taken as the primary variables subject to variation.

2.3 Euler-Lagrange equations

The static behavior of a multilayered FG circular plate with either simply-supported or clamped boundary edges under mechanical loads is studied in the following illustrative examples, in which the material properties are considered as either a two-directional power-law distribution over the radial-thickness surface, while they are independent of the circumferential direction.

The boundary edge at $r=R$ is considered to be either the clamped or simply-supported edge, the corresponding boundary conditions of which are given as follows:

For clamped (C) supports,

$$u_r^{(e)} = u_\theta^{(e)} = u_z^{(e)} = 0. \quad (10a)$$

For simple (S) supports,

$$u_\theta^{(e)} = u_z^{(e)} = \sigma_r^{(e)} = 0. \quad (10b)$$

The continuity conditions at the center of the circular plate ($r=0$) are given as

$$u_r^{(e)} = u_\theta^{(e)} = \tau_{rz}^{(e)} = 0. \quad (11)$$

Using the kinematic and kinetic assumptions, given in Eq. (1), the authors perform the first-order variation of the Reissner energy functional as zero, and then apply the separation of variables combined with the single Fourier series expansion method in the circumferential coordinate. Consequently, the Euler–Lagrange equations of the FG circular plate are obtained as follows:

$$\sum_{m=1}^{N_i} \sum_{e=1}^{N_e} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{I} \mathbf{I}}^{(e)} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{I} \mathbf{III}}^{(e)} & \mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{I} \mathbf{IV}}^{(e)} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{II} \mathbf{III}}^{(e)} & \mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{II} \mathbf{IV}}^{(e)} \\ \mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{III} \mathbf{I}}^{(e)} & \mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{III} \mathbf{II}}^{(e)} & \mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{III} \mathbf{III}}^{(e)} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{IV} \mathbf{I}}^{(e)} & \mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{IV} \mathbf{II}}^{(e)} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{IV} \mathbf{IV}}^{(e)} \end{bmatrix}^{(m)} \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\mathbf{u}}^{(e)} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{w}}^{(e)} \\ \tilde{\boldsymbol{\tau}}^{(e)} \\ \tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}^{(e)} \end{bmatrix}^{(m)} = \delta_{mN_i} \sum_{e=1}^{N_e} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{P}^{(e)} \\ \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix}^{(m)}, \quad (12)$$

where $(\mathbf{K}_{ij}^{(e)})^{(m)} = [(\mathbf{K}_{ji}^{(e)})^{(m)}]^T$ ($i, j = \mathbf{I}, \mathbf{II}, \mathbf{III}, \mathbf{IV}$), and they are not written here for brevity.

By imposing the continuity conditions of each node's nodal primary variables, i.e., the nodal displacement and transverse stress components, at the nodal lines between adjacent prisms, the local stiffness matrix and forcing vector of each prism in Eq. (12) can be assembled as their corresponding global stiffness matrix and forcing vector of the FG circular plate. The nodal primary variables at each node of the prism can then be determined. Subsequently, the variables of the in-plane stresses at the nodes can be obtained using the primary variables.

3 ILLUSTRATIVE EXAMPLES

In this section, the authors examine the static behavior of a one-directional power-law-type FG circular plate with simply-supported boundary conditions under a uniformly distributed load, i.e., $\bar{q}_z^+ = q_0$ and $\bar{q}_z^- = 0$. The problem was previously investigated by Reddy *et al.* (1999) and Saidi *et al.* (2009) using 2D advanced and refined plate theories, such as FSDT, and TSDT, respectively, and was also investigated by Wang *et al.* (2010) using the state space analytical method, and the corresponding

solutions are thus used to validate the solutions obtained using the current R4, R8, R12, T3, T6, and T10 FAPM.

The circular plate considered is composed of ceramic and metal materials according to a one-directional power-law distribution of volume fractions of the constituents through the thickness coordinate. The effective material properties are estimated using the rule of mixtures, in which the Poisson's ratio ν remains a constant (i.e., $\nu=0.288$), while Young's modulus is in the form of

$$E(z) = E_c + (E_m - E_c) \Gamma_m(z), \quad (13)$$

where $\Gamma_m(z)$ denotes the volume fraction of the metal material, and $\Gamma_m(z) = [(1/2) - (z/h)]^{\kappa_{pz}}$. E_m and E_c represent the Young's moduli of the metal and ceramic materials, respectively, and the ratio of E_m/E_c is taken to be 0.396. The superscript, κ_{pz} , denotes the material-property gradient index in the thickness direction. When $\kappa_{pz} = 0$ and $\kappa_{pz} = \infty$, the FG circular plate will reduce to the homogeneous metal and ceramic plates, respectively, while in the cases of other values of κ_{pz} , the top and bottom surfaces of the FGM plate are ceramic- and metal-rich, respectively.

Theories	$h/R=0.05$	$h/R=0.1$	$h/R=0.15$	$h/R=0.2$
Current T3 finite prism method (16x2)	5.1599	5.2086	5.2748	5.3645
Current T3 finite prism method (16x4)	5.5560	5.5971	5.6553	5.7355
Current T3 finite prism method (32x4)	5.5761	5.6113	5.6687	5.7482
Current T3 finite prism method (64x8)	5.6766	5.7117	5.7699	5.8513
Current R4 finite prism method (8x2)	5.7459	5.7808	5.8387	5.9195
Current R4 finite prism method (8x4)	5.7460	5.7808	5.8389	5.9201
Current R4 finite prism method (16x4)	5.7232	5.7584	5.8170	5.8987
Current R4 finite prism method (32x8)	5.7153	5.7508	5.8099	5.8924
Current T6 finite prism method (16x2)	5.7024	5.7408	5.8003	5.8830
Current T6 finite prism method (16x4)	5.7079	5.7466	5.8064	5.8894
Current T6 finite prism method (32x4)	5.7091	5.7449	5.8041	5.8868
Current T6 finite prism method (64x8)	5.7103	5.7457	5.8047	5.8874
Current Q8 finite prism method (16x2)	5.7440	5.7795	5.8385	5.9208
Current Q8 finite prism method (16x4)	5.7445	5.7803	5.8397	5.9227
Current Q8 finite prism method (32x4)	5.7234	5.7590	5.8182	5.9009
Current Q8 finite prism method (64x8)	5.7157	5.7510	5.8100	5.8927
Current T10 finite prism method (8x2)	5.7088	5.7444	5.8037	5.8865
Current T10 finite prism method (8x4)	5.7090	5.7445	5.8038	5.8866
Current T10 finite prism method (16x4)	5.7101	5.7455	5.8046	5.8872
Current T10 finite prism method (32x8)	5.7106	5.7459	5.8048	5.8875
Current C12 finite prism method (8x2)	5.7088	5.7444	5.8037	5.8866
Current C12 finite prism method (8x4)	5.7100	5.7455	5.8046	5.8873
Current C12 finite prism method (16x4)	5.7104	5.7457	5.8047	5.8873
Current C12 finite prism method (32x8)	5.7107	5.7459	5.8048	5.8875
CPT (Reddy <i>et al.</i> 1999)	5.700	5.700	5.700	5.700
FSDT (Reddy <i>et al.</i> 1999)	5.714	5.756	5.826	5.925
TSDT (Saidi <i>et al.</i> 2009)	5.7133	5.7546	5.8232	5.9194
3D solutions (Wang <i>et al.</i> 2010)	5.710	5.745	5.804	5.886

Table 1 Convergence studies for various RMVT-based FAPM solutions of the displacement components at the center of one-directional power-law-type FG circular plates with simply supported boundary conditions and under a uniformly distributed load.

Table 1 shows the convergence studies for the current R4, R8, R12, T3, T6, and T10 FAPM solutions of the displacement components at the center of the FG circular plate with simply-supported boundary conditions under a uniform load. The dimensionless displacement is defined as $\bar{u}_z = [(64 D_c)/(q_0 R^4)] u_z(0, \theta, 0)$, in which $D_c = (E_c h^3)/[12(1-\nu^2)]$. The material-property gradient indices κ_{p_z} of the FG circular plate are considered to be $\kappa_{p_z} = 2$. The aspect ratios (h/R) of the circular plate are taken to be $h/R = 0.05, 0.1, 0.15$, and 0.2 .

It can be seen in Table 1 that the current FAPM solutions are accurate and converge rapidly. The convergent solutions of R4, R8, and R12 FAPM are obtained, when we use an $(n_r \times n_z) = (32 \times 8)$ mesh, as well as an $(n_r \times n_z) = (64 \times 8)$ mesh for the T3, T6, and T10 FAPM. These convergent solutions are shown to be in excellent agreement with the 3D exact solutions [5], quasi-3D SSSDRK solutions [2] and 2D accurate solutions [5-7]. The performance of these FAPM are (R12, T10) > (R8, T6) > (R4, T3), in which the symbol ">" means that the solutions are more accurate and that the convergence rate is faster.

To have a clearer picture with regard to the displacement and stress components induced over the domain of a more general nonhomogeneous circular plate, the authors study the static problem of a bi-directional power-law-type FG circular plate with clamped boundary conditions and under a uniformly distributed load. The Poisson's ratio ν remains a constant (i.e., $\nu = 0.288$), the ratio of E_m/E_c is taken to be 0.396 , and the effective Young's modulus of the FG circular plate are given in the same form as in Eq. (13), while the volume fraction of the metal material Γ_m is defined to obey a bi-directional power-law variation, as follows:

$$\Gamma_m(r, z) = [(1/2) - (z/h)]^{\kappa_{p_z}} [1 - (r/R)]^{\kappa_{p_r}}, \quad (14)$$

where κ_{p_r} denotes the material-property gradient index in the radial direction.

A set of dimensionless variables are given as follows:

$$\bar{u}_z = [(64 D_c)/(q_0 R^4)] u_z(0, \theta, z), \quad (15a)$$

$$(\bar{\sigma}_r, \bar{\tau}_{rz}, \bar{\sigma}_z) = [\sigma_r(0, \theta, z), \tau_{rz}(3R/4, \theta, z), \sigma_z(0, \theta, z)]/q_0. \quad (15b)$$

Figure 3: Through-thickness distributions of (a) in-plane stress component, (b) transverse shear stress component, and (c) transverse normal stress component, induced in a clamped, bi-directional power-law-type FG circular plate for $\kappa_{p_z} = \kappa_{p_r} = 0.5, 1$, and 3

Distributions of the in-plane and transverse stress components through the thickness direction are shown in Fig. 3, in which $h/R = 0.1$ and $\kappa_{p_z} = \kappa_{p_r} = 0.5, 1$ and 3 . The results shown in Fig. 3 indicate that these stress components appear to be the higher-order polynomial function variations through the

thickness direction. The in-plane stress and transverse normal stress components change drastically along the thickness direction when the values of κ_{pz} and κ_{pr} become greater. In the cases of $\kappa_{pz} = \kappa_{pr} = 3$, the maximum in-plane, transverse shear, and transverse normal stress components occur at the top surface, mid-plane, and top surface of the FG circular plate, respectively, the corresponding values of which are $52.99 q_0$, $-5.64 q_0$, and q_0 , i.e., the magnitude ratios among these peak values are about 50: 5: 1 for the moderately thick plate ($h/R=0.1$). Note that the traction conditions on the top and bottom surfaces of the FG plate are exactly satisfied, which should have been hard to achieve when using the principle of virtual displacement (PVD)-based finite element methods in most of the commercial software, such as ANSYS, ABAQUS and NASTRAN.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the authors develop a weak-form formulation of various RMVT-based FAPM to investigate the static behavior of bi-directional power-law-type FG circular plates with simply-supported and clamped edges and under mechanical loads. Implementation of these FAPM shows that their convergent solutions closely agree with each other and that these solutions are in excellent agreement with the 3D exact solutions and 2D accurate solutions available in the literature.

Some 3D static behavior of the bi-directional FG circular plates under mechanical loads is captured in the numerical examples. The through-thickness distribution of the displacement component in the thickness direction appears to be a higher-order polynomial function, rather than a constant as is conventionally assumed to be the case in the 2D advanced and refined plate theories. The results also show that distributions of the in-plane and transverse stress components appear to be much higher-order polynomial functions through the thickness direction, and these variables change drastically along the thickness direction when the material-property gradient indices become greater. These observations are helpful for making the kinematic and kinetic assumptions *a priori* when an advanced or refined plate theory for nonhomogeneous circular plates is to be developed.

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